

Hebridae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) Fauna of the Turkish Thrace Region

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ABSTRACT: : During the field studies carried out in various freshwater habitats in the Thrace Region between 2019-2020, two species from the Hebridae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) family were identified. *Hebrus pilipes* Kanyukova, 1997 was recorded for the first time for the Thrace Region, while the presence of *Hebrus pusillus pusillus* (Fallén, 1807) in Turkish Thrace was confirmed with exact locality records.

KEY WORDS: *Hebrus pilipes*, *Hebrus pusillus pusillus*, Turkish Thrace Region, Türkiye.

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INTRODUCTION

The Hebridae family is represented by 21 species/subspecies (18 species and 3 subspecies) belonging to 2 genera in the Western Palearctic (Kment et al., 2016). 4 species (*Hebrus montanus* Kolenati,

1857, *H. pilipes* Kanyukova, 1997, *H. pusillus pusillus* (Fallén, 1807) and *H. ruficeps* Thomson, 1871) are known to belong to the genus *Hebrus* Curtis, 1833 from this family in Türkiye (Fent et al., 2011; Kment et al., 2016). *H. montanus*, *H. pilipes* and *H. ruficeps* have been

recorded in various localities in the Asian part (Anatolia) of Türkiye (Linnavuori, 1953; Andersen, 1995; Kment & Jindra, 2005; Önder et al., 2006; Fent et al., 2011; Kment et al., 2016, Aukema, 2023). *H. pusillus pusillus* was given from the Thrace Region (European part) without specifying the locality (Oshanin, 1908; Josifov, 1986; Andersen, 1995). It has been reported from different localities by a few researchers from Anatolia (Lindberg, 1922; Hoberlandt, 1952; Linnavuori, 1986; Önder et al., 2006; Kıyak et al., 2008). However, Fent et al. (2011) state that the *H. pusillus pusillus* records given by Hoberlandt (1952) in Türkiye (Anatolia) were misidentification and that these records belong to *H. montanus* and *H. pilipes* species.

According to Kment et al. (2016), all recently revised previous records of *H. pusillus pusillus* from Türkiye, Transcaucasia,

Iran, and Central Asia are misidentifications of other species and include Morocco, Algeria, Libya, Egypt, Sinai, Israel, Syria, Türkiye and Iran records need to be confirmed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was carried out in all kinds of natural and artificial wetlands such as lakes, ponds, dams, rivers, streams, irrigation canals and their surroundings and marsh areas in the Thrace Region between May and September when Heteroptera species were active between 2019-2020 (Table 1, fig. 1). The research material was collected, from the water surface and the waterside with nets and plankton scoop. The obtained samples were taken into tubes containing 70% alcohol. Kanyukova (1997) was used to identify the species.

Table 1. Localities, coordinates, heights and dates where materials were collected in the summer period of 2019-2020 in the Wetlands of Thrace Region.

Loc. No:	Localities	Altitudes	Coordinates	Collecting dates
1	Kırklareli-Ürünlü (stream)	115m	41°40'430"N 26°59'478"E	17.05.2019
2	Çanakale- Gelibolu -Yolağzı Village (Uzunhızırli Pond)	48m	40°18'127N 26°23'496E	26.05.2019
3	İstanbul-Eyüpsultan- Ağaçlı Village- roadside (stream)	17m	41°15'885N 28°53'719E	07.07.2019
4	İstanbul-Çatalaca- Ormanlı (stream)	5m	41°23'414N 28°26'999E	09.07.2019
5	İstanbul-Çatalaca- Danamandıra (stream)	232m	41°19'327N 28°15'948E	10.07.2019
6	İstanbul-Çatalaca- Kūçüksinikli (swamp)	217m	41°13'787N 28°10'596E	11.07.2019
7	Edirne-Yeniköy (Dobrah Stream)	57m	41°21'073N 26°44'786E	08.06.2020
8	Edirne-Uzunköprü-Kurtbey (stream)	35m	41°7'410N 26°33'742E	09.06.2020
9	Edirne-İpsala-İbriktepe (Sultanköy Pond)	46m	41°1'809N 26°29'188E	09.06.2020
10	Kırklareli-between Erikler-Karahamza (stream)	371m	41°53'570N 27°6'220E	17.06.2020
11	Tekirdağ-Naipköy (stream)	27m	40°52'624N 27°24'608E	18.06.2020
12	Edirne-between Hatıpköy-Büyükismailçe (stream)	53m	41°48'445N 26°31'098E	19.06.2020
13	Tekirdağ-Malkara-Sağlamtaş (Aksakal Stream)	82m	40°46'535N 27°3'986E	17.08.2020
14	Tekirdağ-Şarköy-Yayaköy (puddle)	318m	40°42'390N 27°11'763E	17.08.2020
15	Kırklareli-Vize-Kıyıköy Road (stream)	77m	41°37'255N 27°59'249E	18.08.2020

Figure 1. Map showing the localities where *Hebrus pilipes* and *Hebrus pusillus pusillus* are found in the Thrace Region (Google Earth).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

HEBRIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

Hebrus Curtis, 1833

Hebrus pilipes Kanyukova, 1997

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Çanakkale province: Gelibolu-Yolağzı Village (Uzunhızırılı Pond), 28.05.2019, 1♀; **Edirne province:** İpsala-İbriktepe (Sultanköy Pond), 09.06.2020, 1♀; Uzunköprü-Kurtbey (stream), 09.06.2020, 1♀; **İstanbul province:** Eyüpsultan-Ağaçlı Village (stream), 02.07.2019, 1♂; Çatalca-Danamandır (stream), 04.07.2019, 1♂; Silivri-Küçüksinekli (swamp), 04.07.2019, 2♀♀; **Kırklareli province:** Ürünlü (stream),

07.07.2019, 1♀; **Tekirdağ province:** Malkara-Sağlamtaş (Aksakal Stream), 17.08.2020, 1♀; Şarköy-Yayaköy (puddle), 17.08.2020, 1♀, 1♂.

First record for the Turkish Thrace.

Distribution in Türkiye: Asian Türkiye: Antalya, Konya, Mersin, Sivas, Tunceli (Hoberlandt, 1952; Kment & Jindra 2005; Fent et al., 2011).

Distribution in Palearctic: Europe: Russia (South European Territory), Ukraine (Crimea). **Asia:** Azerbaijan, Afghanistan, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Armenia, China (Northwestern Territory), Georgia, Iran, Tadzhikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2023).

***Hebrus pusillus pusillus* (Fallén, 1807)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE:
Edirne province: Between Hatipköy-Büyükismailçe (stream), 19.06.2020, 1♀; Yeniköy (Dobralı Stream), 08.08.2020, 1♀;
İstanbul province: Çatalca-Ormanlı Village (stream), 03.07.2019, 1♀; **Kırklareli province:** Between Erikler-Karahamza (stream), 17.06.2019, 2♂♂; Vize-Kıyıköy road (stream), 18.08.2020, 3♀♀, 4♂♂;
Tekirdağ province: Naipköy (stream), 18.06.2020, 1♀.

First exact records from Turkish Thrace Region.

Distribution in Türkiye: European Türkiye: Thrace (Oshanin, 1908; Josifov, 1986; Andersen, 1995, Aukema, 2023).
Asian Türkiye?: Aydın, Bolkar Mountain (Bulgar Dağı), Hatay, İzmir (Lindberg, 1922; Linnavuori, 1986; Önder et al., 2006; Kıyak et al., 2008; Aukema, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Türkiye, Finland, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Montenegro, Moldavia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Central European Territory, North European Territory, South European Territory), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine.
North Africa: Algeria? Canary Islands, Egypt? Libya? Morocco? **Asia:** Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye? Iran? Israel? Lebanon? Russia (East Siberia, Far East, West Siberia), Syria? (Kment et al., 2016; Aukema, 2023).

Two species from the Hebridae family were identified as a result of the identification of samples collected from various aquatic habitats in the Thrace Region between 2019-2020. *Hebrus pilipes* have been recorded from several localities in the south and central part of Anatolia (Fent et al., 2011). In the Palearctic Region, it is known in Europe only from the Southern European part of Russia and Ukraine, and in Asia from Afghanistan, Kazakhstan,

Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan and the Northwestern part of China, including Georgia, Armenia and Iran, neighboring Anatolia (Aukema, 2023). *Hebrus pusillus pusillus* has a fairly wide distribution in Europe, including Bulgaria and Greece, neighboring the Thrace Region (Aukema, 2023), but records from Iran, Israel, Lebanon and Syria including Anatolia (Asian Türkiye) in Asia and in North Africa need to be confirmed (Fent et al., 2011; Kment et al., 2016).

H. pilipes differs morphologically from other species by its scutellum (more or less raised in apical half) and, in the male, its hind tibiae, which is thickened in the middle and contains a row of long hairs on the upper side and several rows of shorter hairs on the inner sides (Fig. 2b-c). *H. pusillus pusillus* differs from *H. pilipes* and other species by its scutellum structure (more or less rounded at the apex and not incised) and a row of hairs extending from the middle to the apical in the inner part of the hind tibiae in the male (Fig. 3b).

These two similar species are also distinguished by the following additional characteristics: *H. pusillus pusillus* is dark brown and the antennae and dorsal of the legs are reddish brown to dark brown, ventral side of legs pale brown, but not yellow (Fig. 3a), in *H. pilipes* the head scutellum and corium are reddish brown (sometimes the body is dark color), the first and second segments of the antennae and legs yellow, only distal of the femora, proximal of tibiae and first tarsal segments darkened (Fig. 2a) (see Kanyukova, 1997).

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Figure 2. a. *Hebrus pilipes*, male (Tekirdağ province: Şarköy-Yayaköy, body length 2 mm), b-c. Hind tibiae (b.dorsal, c.ventral)

Figure 3. a. *Hebrus pusillus pusillus*, male (Kırklareli province: Between Erikler-Karahamza, body length 1,9 mm) b. Hind tibiae (ventral)

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